

0.92 and 1.68 and these also support the Oh symmetry of the complexes^{1,4,15}.

The cobalt(II) complexes are also paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values of 5.12 B.M. Since these values may correspond to a tetrahedral or octahedral configuration, the μ_{eff} at two low temperatures was also determined and given below.

Complex	303K	257K	143K
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	5.12 B.M.	4.98 B.M.	4.96 B.M.
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	5.46 B.M.	5.00 B.M.	5.14 B.M.
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N})_2]$	5.20 B.M.	5.18 B.M.	5.32 B.M.

It is clear that the values are independent of temperature and hence correspond to an octahedral geometry with T ground state. In the tetrahedral structures with A ground term, on the other hand, the values increase considerably with temperature. In the spectra also three sharp bands are seen clearly at 22,00, 16,00 and 7.57 kK assigned as ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{P})(\nu_3)$, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{1g}(\text{F})(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})(\nu_1)$ corresponding to octahedral geometry. The ν_3 band is mostly split into two components, one at 22.83 kK and the other at 18.86 kK. The Dq, B and β values are around 757 cm^{-2} , 960 cm^{-1} and 0.98 and correspond to the assigned geometry^{16,17}.

This discussion clearly indicates that the Schiff bases used in the study function as strong ligands and the β values indicate the presence of large covalent character on complexes. The splitting of ν_2 band in Ni(II) and ν_3 band in Co(II) complexes is due to the lowering of symmetry upon coordination.

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Some Reactions of 8-Quinolinol-N-oxide with Bis(η^5 -Cyclopentadienyl)titanium Dichloride

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ANDRAE used sodamide in boiling benzene or toluene as a suitable condensing base for the preparation of phenoxy derivatives of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride¹. Survey of literature indicates that the reaction of 8-quinolinol with (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂TiCl₂ has been reported² but there is no mention of the reaction of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide with (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂TiCl₂. This note deals with the preparation of N-oxido-8-quinolinolates of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride.

Experimental

The preparations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Benzene, toluene, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran were purified and dried. Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride³ and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide⁴ were prepared by the reported methods. Titanium was estimated gravimetrically, chlorine by Volhards' method and carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen by the microcombustion procedure.

NMR spectrum was recorded in CDCl₃ on Perkin-Elmer R-32. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer Infracord model-621 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets.

Preparation of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)-N-oxido-8-quinolinolato titanium chloride, (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂-(C₉H₈O₂N)TiCl: Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride (0.415 g; 0.0016 mole) and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (0.536 g; 0.0032 mole) were added to a suspension of sodamide (5 g) in toluene (200 ml). The mixture was refluxed with constant stirring for 30 min. The cooled mixture was filtered through a sintered glass funnel (porosity G-4) and the filtrate concentrated to ~ 20 ml and treated with petroleum ether. A slight brown coloured crystalline compound was obtained, which was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. It was soluble in benzene, chloroform, THF, etc., did not melt below 315° and turned dark on heating. (Found: C, 60.5; H, 4.3; N, 3.6; Ti, 12.78, Cl, 9.6. (C₉H₈)₂-(C₉H₈O₂N)TiCl requires C, 61; H, 4.3; N, 3.7; Ti, 12.85; Cl, 9.5%).

Preparation of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)di(N-oxido-8-quinolinolato)titanium, (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂(C₉H₈O₂N)₂Ti: Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride (0.45 g; 0.0016 mole) and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (0.538 g; 0.0032 mole) were dissolved in dry acetonitrile (40 ml) [or benzene (200 ml)]. To this was added 0.34 g (0.0032 mole) of triethylamine with constant shaking. A yellow crystalline compound settled down, which was allowed to stand over night. The

solid was filtered off, washed with acetonitrile to remove triethylamine hydrochloride (when benzene was used as a solvent, the mixture was stirred mechanically for ~48 hr, both triethylamine hydrochloride and the compound were precipitated, from which the former was removed by repeated washing with acetonitrile). Yellow crystalline compounds were obtained in both the cases which were found identical in their ir spectra and elemental analysis. The compound was insoluble in almost all organic solvents. It did not melt below 315° but turned dark on heating.

Its composition corresponded to $(C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)_2Ti$. (Found : C, 67.1 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 5.45 ; Ti, 9.8. $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)_2Ti$ requires C, 67.4 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 5.6 ; Ti, 9.64%).

Results and Discussion

The nmr spectrum of *bis*(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)-N-oxido-8-quinolinolate titanium chloride, $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)TiCl$, taken in $CDCl_3$ exhibits two types of protons belonging to quinoline ring protons at δ 7.2-7.3 ppm and the others due to cyclopentadienyl ring protons at δ 6.55 ppm in the ratio of 3 : 5. This confirmed the presence of two cyclopentadienyl rings and one N-oxido-8-quinolinolate group in the molecule. As $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)_2Ti$ is insoluble in $CDCl_3$, its nmr spectrum could not be recorded.

The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} in KBr pellets. The presence of cyclopentadienyl group⁵ is indicated by a C-H stretching at 3040 cm^{-1} , a C-H in plane bending at 1105 cm^{-1} and 1020 cm^{-1} and C-C stretching at 1430 cm^{-1} and the quinoline ring⁶ by sharp bands at 1570, 1500, 1380 and 1350 cm^{-1} , in both the compounds.

On complexation of heterocyclic N-oxides with metals, the N-O stretching and N-O bending modes are affected^{7,8}. However, in the case of quinoline-N-oxide the N-O stretching band shifts to higher frequencies in 3d metal complexes ; this may be attributed to the impurity of N-O stretching band and an extensive metal to ligand π -bonding^{9,10}. In the present complexes of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide, the N-O stretching is shown by a sharp band at 1310 cm^{-1} as is shown by the free ligand¹¹.

A doublet in the free ligand at 885-875 cm^{-1} has been inferred to be due to N-O bending modes coupled with δ -OH in-plane bending¹². In the spectra of all these complexes, a broad band in the region 950-800 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 840 cm^{-1} and a maximum at 820 cm^{-1} is observed. Since the sharp band at 820 cm^{-1} is due to C-H out-of-plane bending the shoulder at 840 cm^{-1} may be due to N-O bending.

In the far ir region, a band of medium intensity is observed at 350 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)TiCl$, which may be due to Ti-Cl stretching¹³. In the spectra of both the complexes,

two bands of medium intensity are observed at 520-500 cm^{-1} and ~400 cm^{-1} region. These may be due to Ti-O stretching at Ti-O-C and Ti-O-N sites, respectively, as have also been observed in metal-8-quinolinolates¹⁴ at 540-510 cm^{-1} , metal-N-oxido-quinolinolate¹² at ~530 cm^{-1} and metal chelates of aromatic amine oxides^{15,16} at ~440 cm^{-1} .

The observation of two Ti-O stretching bands in the complexes suggest that 8-quinoline-N-oxide acts as a bidentate ligand in N-oxido-8-quinolinolate complexes of titanium reported here.

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Formation Constants of Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} Complexes of N-4-Acylac-naphthylidene-*o*-Aminophenol

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THE successive stability constants of the complexes of N-4-acylacnaphthylidene-*o*-aminophenol with various trivalent metal ions have been determined at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and 0.1 *M* ionic strength and are reported in this communication. The order of stabilities of

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